

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIFFERENCES IN FIELD SOIL MOISTURE AT SOYBEAN SOWING DUE TO DIFFERENT ANNUAL METEOROLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract

The content of soil moisture in different soil horizons of soybean fields in the 0-150 cm layer was studied in years with different meteorological conditions, including separately for the bare and cénosis soils. The value of moisture reserves in the soil during the spring sowing period are determined by the total amount of precipitation and their relative index (RPI) in the previous period of soil water accumulation (September-April). During the growing season, water losses from bare soil occur mainly from the arable layer; the decrease in the total moisture reserves of the deep layers of the soil of the soybean cénosis is mainly associated with plants.

Keywords: soybean cénosis, soil moisture, relative precipitation index (RPI).

Any decrease in non-beneficial water consumption must result in increased production per unit of consumed water (Blum A., Perry C. et al., 2009). Increasing the efficient water use by cultivated soybean *Glycine max* (L.) Merr. requires an accurate assessment of the moisture reserves of soybean fields in different seasons (Харчук О., 2019). The aim of the work was to assess the content of soil moisture in different soil horizons of agrocénoses in the 0-150 cm layer in years with different meteorological conditions, including separately for the bare and cénosis soils.

The studies were carried out in 2017 -2022 at the fields of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection (IGFPP), mainly in the cénoses of the Aura variety with traditional cultivation technology (400*10³ plants/ha, row spacing 45 cm). To assess meteorological conditions was used the relative precipitation index (RPI) - the ratio of precipitation sum for the given period *P* and the long term average for the same period *P* expressed in percent, $RPI = P/\bar{P} * 100\%$; for long period (quarter, year) are such criteria of RPI value: 0-49,9% (extremely dry), 50,0-74,9% (very dry), 75,0-89,9% (dry) and 90,0-110,0% (average) (Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędski L., 2002). Gravimetric soil moisture samples were taken by hand drill AM-26 at 10-20 cm depth increments to 150 cm deep (both in cénosis and on bare soil). For each horizon, soil samples were taken in triplicate. To determine soil moisture, the samples were dried in an oven at 105 °C to

constant weight (Black C., 1965). To determine the volumetric soil moisture content, the gravimetric data were multiplied by the soil density values, obtained experimentally (Вадюнина А.Ф., Корчагина З.А., 1986; ISO 11272).

The period from autumn to spring in Moldova is slightly dry, as evidenced by the comparison of precipitation during this period with average annual for years 2001-2018 (Table 1). Of the previous years, 1983 was the driest (in total only 463 mm after 431 mm in 1982), of which 168 mm of precipitation fell on the "winter" 1982/1983 and 236 mm on the summer, June-August 1983.

Two consecutive seasons (2018-2019 and 2019-2020), the period from autumn to spring in Moldova was atypically dry (180,0 and 108,4 mm), as evidenced by the comparison of precipitation during this period with average annual 326 ± 26 mm (Table 1). Prior to this season (2022), the period from September 2021 to April 2022 in Moldova was also atypically dry too (69,6 mm).

The definition of drought has continually been a stumbling block for drought monitoring and analysis. Wilhite D. and Glantz M. (1985) completed a thorough review of dozens of drought definitions and identified different overall categories, from meteorological and climatological to agricultural, hydrologic and water management.

Table 1.

The amount of precipitation for the autumn-spring period in Moldova and the IGFPP in different years.

Years (autumn-spring)	Autumn-spring precipitation, mm		
	September-December	January-April	Σ
average (2009-2018)	168 ± 30	158 ± 3	326 ± 26
2016-2017	169,2	159,7	328,9
2017-2018	168,3	174,3	342,6
2018-2019	96,2	83,2	180,0
2019-2020	60,0	48,4	108,4
2020-2021	222,6	86,4	309,0
2021-2022	64,4	103,6	168,0

Note. Data for 2016-2018 refers to Moldova (Climatic Research Unit Country File created on Wed 15 May 2019 11:43:38 BST, from CRU TS run #1905011326), later, for 2019-2022 - directly to the fields of the IGFPP (<http://surl.li/cywwu>).

The *relative precipitation index (RPI)* is the ratio of precipitation sum for the given period P and the long term average for the same period P^* expressed in percent: $RPI = (P/P^*) \times 100\%$; this index was proposed for relatively long period, from quarter to year (Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędzki L., 2002). Regarding the normal average RPI value (90,0÷110,9%), in ac-

cordance with the actual precipitation the autours proposed different classes of total precipitation for long dry periods: 75,0÷89,9 (dry), 50,0÷74,9 (very dry), 0÷49,9% (extremely dry).

In Table 2 are presented the data on the relative precipitation index (RPI) for the autumn-spring period of water accumulation in soil (from September to April) in different years.

Table 2.

The relative precipitation index (RPI) for the autumn-spring period in Moldova and the IGFPP in different years.

(«autumn», IX-XII-«spring», I-IV)	September-December	January-April	Σ
average (2009-2018)	100	100	100
2016-2017	101	101	101
2017-2018	100	110	105
2018-2019	57	53	55
2019-2020	36	31	33
2020-2021	132	55	95
2021-2022	38	66	52

Table 3 shows the gravimetric soil moisture data at soybean sowing, obtained in different years. Before sowing-2020, soil moisture at all soil depths is significantly lower than in previous years. In the first half-meter, the soil moisture content is 5-6% lower than the values of previous years.

Table 4 shows the volumetric soil moisture data at soybean sowing, obtained in different years. The water content in the layer 0-40 cm is not the best parameter of total water balance accordingly to RPI and to the total value of precipitations during long period of water accumulation (from September to April). Only before sowing-2020, soil moisture at all soil depths is significantly lower than in previous years.

As can be seen from Tables 1, 2 and 4, in the autumn-spring period of water accumulation in soil (from September to April) out of 6 years of research, three years (2017, 2018 and 2021) were characterized by precipitations above the average long-term norm (326 mm): 329, 343 and 309 mm, respectively, with RPI values of 101, 105 and 95% (this is within the normal range, which is 90.0÷110.9%). As can be seen from Table 4, after the autumn-spring period of moisture accumulation, these three years (2017, 2018 and 2021) were characterized by the maximum total water reserves in the 0-150 cm soil layer: 417, 380 and 391 mm, respectively.

Table 3.

Gravimetric soil moisture in the field at soybean sowing in different years (2017-2022).

Soil layer, cm	Gravimetric soil moisture during sowing, % of dry soil mass					
	2017 (May, 5)	2018 (May, 7)	2019 (Apr, 25)	2020 (May, 20)	2021 (May, 11)	2022 (Apr., 15)
0-10	25,0 ±0,2	12,4 ±3,1	17,1 ±0,9	11,0 ±2,3	20,7 ±1,0	21,0 ±0,5
10-20	24,2 ±0,2	17,1 ±0,1	18,8 ±0,5	15,2 ±0,2	20,7 ±0,2	22,8 ±0,4
20-30	21,8 ±0,6	17,9 ±0,2	17,8 ±0,4	14,2 ±0,4	20,3 ±0,2	20,9 ±0,2
30-40	20,8 ±0,2	18,1 ±0,1	17,1 ±0,1	13,0 ±0,4	19,2 ±0,3	20,9 ±0,4
40-60	20,8 ±0,3	20,2 ±0,3	18,3 ±0,1	13,2 ±0,1	16,7 ±0,4	15,4 ±0,1
60-80	19,5 ±0,3	20,6 ±0,0	17,9 ±0,1	13,1 ±0,4	18,2 ±0,2	14,9 ±0,2
80-100	21,5 ±0,1	20,0 ±0,1	17,0 ±0,3	11,1 ±0,2	17,8 ±0,5	15,6 ±0,3
100-120	20,6 ±0,2	19,3 ±0,4	16,8 ±0,1	12,1 ±0,2	15,6 ±0,7	14,7 ±0,6
120-140	19,1 ±0,5	17,8 ±0,1	16,4 ±0,3	-	14,1 ±0,6	13,4 ±0,2
140-150	15,7 ±0,2	17,9 ±0,1	16,8 ±0,4	11,8 ±0,1	13,2 ±0,3	13,4 ±0,3

As can be seen from Tables 1, 2 and 4, in the autumn-spring period of water accumulation in soil (from September to April), out of 6 years of research, three years (2019, 2020 and 2022) were characterized by precipitations significantly less than the average annual norm (326 mm): in 2019 and in 2022, 180 mm and 168 mm, respectively, with RPI values of 55% and 52% (very dry, 50,0÷74,9%); in 2020 precipitations in total

were minimal, 108 mm, with an RPI value of 33% (extremely dry 0÷49,9%). As can be seen from Table 4, after the autumn-spring period of water accumulation, these three years (2019, 2020 and 2022) were characterized by the minimum total water reserves in the 0-150 cm soil layer: 354 and 333 mm in 2019 and 2022, respectively. and the smallest value, 256 mm, was in 2020.

Table 4.

Soil layer, cm	Volumetric soil moisture reserves at sowing, mm					
	2017 (May, 5)	2018 (May, 7)	2019 (Apr, 25)	2020 (May, 20)	2021 (May, 11)	2022 (Apr., 15)
0-40	117±2	84±3	90±4	69±2	113±5	109±3
40-150	300±3	296±4	264±2	187±2	278±3	224±2
0-150	417±3	380±5	354±3	256±3	391±4	333±2

Thus, during soybean sowing, the total water reserves in the 0-150 cm soil layer fully corresponded to the amount of precipitation and RPI values for the autumn-spring period (September-April), decreasing from seasons with a normal RPI value (average $100 \pm 3\%$ for 2017, 2018 and 2021) to seasons with a low RPI value: on average $54 \pm 2\%$ for 2019 and 2022, and especially to the 2020 season with a minimum RPI value of 33%: total water reserves in the 0-150 cm soil layer decreased from seasons from normal RPI value to seasons with a low RPI value: for 2017, 2018 and 2021, the total water reserves in soil layer 0-150 cm were on average 396 ± 11 mm, and for 2019 and 2022, the total water reserves were on average 344 ± 11 mm; by sowing-2020, the total water reserves in the 0-150 cm layer are especially small, 256 ± 3 mm.

When comparing the seasonal changes (years 2019 and 2022) in total moisture reserves in the cenosis with areas of bare soil it was found that water losses in black fallow occur mainly from the arable layer. When sowing 2019 (April, 25) was 354 mm (264 ± 2 mm in the layer 40-150 cm), but at harvesting-2019 (September, 6) left in cenosis 218 ± 4 mm (167 ± 2 mm in the layer 40-150 cm; at fallow plot - 305 ± 5 mm (238 ± 1 mm in the layer 40-150 cm). When sowing 2022 (April, 15) was 333 mm (214 ± 2 mm in the layer 40-150 cm), but to 102 days after planting (DAP), July, 26 in cenosis left 179 ± 3 mm (142 ± 2 mm in the layer 40-150 cm; at fallow plot left 281 mm (220 ± 2 mm in the layer 40-150 cm). In 2022 on black fallow for period 102 DAP a decrease in soil moisture (near 60 mm relative to sowing) occurred exclusively in the 0-40 cm layer. In both years, in soybean cenosis the moisture reserves in the soil layer 40-150 cm decreased more, then in the fallow plot (minimum by 80 mm).

Conclusion

The value of moisture reserves in the soil layer 0-150 cm during the spring sowing period are determined by the total amount of precipitation and their relative index (RPI) in the previous period of soil water accumulation (September-April). During the growing season, water losses from bare soil occur mainly from the arable layer; the decrease in the total moisture reserves of the deep layers of the soil of the soybean cenosis is mainly associated with plants.

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